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Study Habit and Peer-Group Influence as Predictors of Senior Secondary School Students' Learning Outcome in Chemistry in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study evaluated peer-group influence and study habit on students' learning outcome in Chemistry in Rivers State. The research method adopted in this study was ex-post facto research design (after effect). The population of the study was 20,658 Chemistry students made up students in public and private schools in Rivers State. Multi-stage sampling method was used for the study. Simple random sampling was used to put the students into three senatorial zones; proportional stratified sampling was used to obtain 130 students from each senatorial zone (stratum) while stratified sampling was used to select 195 science students each from public and private schools. Again, proportional sampling technique was used to select six (6) senior secondary schools in Rivers State; one public and one private school in each stratum while intact classes were used. The sample size of 390 students was drawn from the population of the study using Taro Yamane's formula. Two research instruments, Student Study Habit Inventory (SSHI) $r = .80$, Peer-Group Inventory (PGI) $r = .85$ and Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) ($r = .73$), were used for data collection. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 significance level. Study habit was significant on students' academic performance in Chemistry. Students with positive peer influence performed better than the students while urban students performed better than the rural students. Peer group influenced academic performance of students in Chemistry in Rivers State. School authorities, parents and government should encourage children to adopt good study habits through provision of developmental programmes that will help students build efficient and effective study habit towards learning in an early stage of their studies.

Keywords: Study habit, peer-group influence, predictors, students, learning outcome.